

The Cell Cycle Ontology: An application ontology for the representation and integrated analysis of the cell cycle process

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Abstract

The Cell Cycle Ontology (CCO) is an application ontology that automatically captures and integrates detailed knowledge on the cell cycle process by combining, interlinking and enriching knowledge from various sources. CCO uses Semantic Web technologies, and it is accessible via the web for browsing, visualising, advanced querying, and computational reasoning. CCO facilitates a detailed analysis of cell cycle related molecular network components. Through querying and automated reasoning, it may provide new hypotheses to help steer a systems biology approach to biological network building.

Rationale

Molecular biology has spent the last two decades cataloguing genes, expression levels, proteins, molecular interactions, and more. The combination of all these catalogues should enable a biologist to start building a comprehensive picture of a biological system, rather than looking at only the individual components.

Formation of these components into a network that describes a biological system constitutes a first step in allowing a biologist to develop an understanding of the behaviour of a system. If adequate kinetic and other parameters can be obtained or estimated, such models can be used for network simulations in a mathematical framework, making them particularly useful to study emergent properties of such a system [1–5]. These models provide the basis to much of systems biology that is built on integrative data analysis and mathematical modelling [6–9]. In systems biology, dynamic simulations with a model of a biological process serve as a means to validate the model’s architecture and parameters and to provide hypotheses for new experiments.

Complementary to such model-dependent hypothesis generation, the field of computational reasoning promises to provide a powerful additional source of new hypotheses about biological network components. The integration of biological knowledge from various sources and the alignment of their representations into one common representation are recognised as critical steps toward hypothesis building [10, 11]. Such an integrated information resource is essential for exploration and exploitation by both humans and computers, in the case of computers *via* automated reasoning [12].

Bio-ontologies

While it is easy to compare nucleic acid or polypeptide sequences from different bioinformatics resources, the biological knowledge contained in these resources is very difficult to compare, as it is represented in a wide variety of lexical forms [13–15], and there are no tools that facilitate an easy comparison and integration of knowledge in this form. This is where ontologies can provide help.

Ontologies represent knowledge about a specific scientific domain and support a consistent and unambiguous representation of entities within that domain. This knowledge can be integrated into a single model that holds these domain entities, their term labels as well as their connecting relationships [16]. A well-known example of such an ontology is the Gene Ontology (GO) [17]. An ontology, therefore, links term labels to their interpretations, *i.e.* specifications of their meanings, defined as a set of properties.

Ontologies not only provide the foundation for knowledge integration, but also the basis for advanced computational reasoning to validate hypotheses and make implicit knowledge explicit [18, 19]. Integrated knowledge founded on well-defined semantics provides a framework to enable computers to conceptually handle knowledge in a manner comparable to the handling of numerical data: it allows a computer to process expressed facts, look for patterns and make inferences, thereby extending the human thinking

about complex information. On a more technical level, computational reasoning services can also be used to check consistency of such integrated knowledge, to re-engineer the design of parts of the whole ontology or to design entirely new extensions that comply with the current knowledge [20].

In general, ontologies that model domain knowledge are developed through an iterative process of refinement, an approach common in the field of software engineering [21]. Ontology development has been pursued for many years, and while several methodologies have been proposed [22–29], none has been widely accepted. The Open Biomedical Ontology (OBO) project [30], however, aims to co-ordinate the development of bio-ontologies (*e.g.* the GO and the Relation Ontology (RO) [31], among many others). The OBO foundry [32] has provided a set of principles to guide the development of ontologies. These ontologies have gained a wide acceptance in the biomedical community [33], as a means for data annotation, integration, and as a reference.

Biological information is known to be hard to integrate and analyse [34]. One of the reasons is that biologists are inclined to invent new names and expressions, *e.g.* for proteins and their functions, that others have already named. This has led to the high incidence of synonymy, homonymy and polysemy that plague biomedicine. Furthermore, biological knowledge is often not crisp, as evidenced by the wide-spread use of quantifiers such as ‘often’, ‘usually’ and ‘sometimes’. Finally, the sheer volume and complexity of biological data and the diversity of representational formats provide profound challenges for efficient biomedical knowledge management. Altogether this calls for a concerted effort of experts from the biomedical and computational sciences to organise and facilitate the integration and exploitation of the rapidly accumulating biological information.

Application ontologies in life sciences and their role in systems biology approaches

Application ontologies define relevant concepts for a particular application or use [35]. They can be built by combining domain ontologies (or parts of domain ontologies), serving as a *reference*, and they can be extended according to the needs of a particular application. Application ontologies are intended to be directly embedded into knowledge bases on which different applications can be run, such as data mining and hypothesis generation. Application ontologies can play an important role in exploiting the formalisation of domain knowledge, and thereby facilitating the integration of different types of information (*e.g.* knowledge about biological processes and subcellular localisations, both parts of GO). Figure 1 shows a sample knowledge element composed of such integrated information. This schematic representation gives

a minimal, but context-linked, notion of a specific protein and its environment of functional characteristics (*e.g.* where it is located, in which processes it participates, by which gene it is encoded, *etc.*).

A successful application ontology may form the core of an efficient and effective management system. Such a system combines data extraction methods, data format conversions and a variety of information sources. To illustrate the potential use of application ontologies for the biosciences we have designed and built a knowledge management system that facilitates the analysis of cell cycle control.

Why focusing on the cell cycle process?

The eukaryotic cell cycle, or cell division cycle, is the series of events that happen between two consecutive cell divisions that underlie cell multiplication. The molecular events that control the cell cycle are ordered and directional, *i.e.*, each process occurs in a sequential fashion and it is impossible to reverse the cycle. The cell cycle control network is complex and is thought to include hundreds of proteins [36,37].

Although the basic principles of cell cycle control are now well-documented [38], we are far from a complete understanding of all the intricacies of the system. A deeper knowledge of the cell cycle control system is essential to the understanding of the growth and development of eukaryotic organisms. This is in turn necessary in order to be able to combat numerous diseases in which cell cycle aberrations are involved, such as cancer.

Part of this knowledge has already been incorporated into dynamic system models that are being exploited to test, refine and generate hypotheses [39]. This holistic and integrative approach in biological research, also called systems biology, is gaining momentum [40,41] and it is leading to novel insights into the cell machinery [36,42,43]. To further augment the cell cycle research with computational approaches, we have built the Cell Cycle Ontology (CCO), which integrates a wide variety of knowledge pertinent to the cell cycle. Such integration will afford a wider input in to various systems approaches.

Results and Discussion

The CCO application ontology

CCO is built to provide laboratory biologists with a one-stop shop for cell cycle knowledge and to obtain an integrated knowledge system that can be used to explore the potential power of automated reasoning. CCO comprises information from a number of resources that contain relevant information about the cell

cycle process, such as GO [44], RO, the IntAct database [45], the NCBI taxonomy [46], the UniProt knowledge base [47], and putative orthology relationships derived with the OrthoMCL clustering algorithm [48, 49]. All the information is integrated in a single framework supported by the ontologies. The integrated knowledge system supports queries not feasible with the original, individual and separate information sources.

Bio-ontologies and their presentations have been made accessible through existing software tools (such as OBO-Edit [50], Protégé [51]), or web-based tools, such as BioPortal [52], which can be used to create new terms and relationships and to explore and analyse these ontologies. The most frequently used biomedical ontologies are provided in the Open Biomedical Ontology Format (OBOF) [53], while some are also natively available in the Web Ontology Language (OWL) [54] (though the OBO format can be transformed into an OWL representation [55–58]). OWL provides a means to create semantically rich ontologies with ample possibilities for querying and computational reasoning. Therefore, we converted the wealth of information available in the OBOF and the highly curated information from public data sources into the more expressive OWL representation to exploit richer forms of computational reasoning.

CCO is extensible and the CCO integration architecture can accommodate additional ontologies as necessary. In addition, a broad range of export formats from CCO (in particular OWL and Resource Description Framework (RDF)) enables virtual integration with external sources (controlled vocabularies translated into RDF, such as MeSH [59]), allowing queries that address these disparate resources through Semantic Web technologies [60, 61].

Knowledge representation in CCO

CCO is a resource that can directly support systems biology. Systems biology is essentially a model driven approach to biological research, in which a model of a biological process serves to integrate all the available information (network components and their interactions). A model simulation allows an understanding of the network behaviour, including changes to the entities, describing these changes in terms of *what* these entities are, *where* they are located and *when* these statements hold. To this end, the knowledge of entities and their interactions needs to be represented in a mathematical framework that facilitates dynamic simulations.

Similarly, to computationally reason about temporal and spatial aspects of a biological process, this knowledge should be represented by a semantically rich and strict language (*i.e.* OWL) to exploit

automatic reasoning tools. Automated reasoners for OWL do not directly support either temporal or spatial reasoning. It is, however, possible to make representations of temporal and spatial aspects of knowledge and then reason about them in a way adequate for many application settings.

Within cell cycle related research, a scientist may be interested in a particular protein (what) for which the localisation (where) and the specific phase of the cell cycle (when) are important analysis components. To represent the linkage between all these different terms, CCO uses relationships as follows. Let

- B be a protein;
- C be a cellular location in which B might be present;
- G be the gene that codes for B;
- P be a biological process in which B participates;
- I be an interaction in which B takes part; and
- T be the organism that is the source of B.

These relationships provide the basis for atomic elements of knowledge about the protein B: “B located in C”, “B coded by G”, “B participates in P”, “B participates in I”, and “B has source T”. The existing relationships also have an inverse relationship such as “P has participant B”, “G codes for B”, “C location of B”, “T source of B”. An example is shown in Figure 1.

CCO contents

CCO supports four model organisms: *H. sapiens*, *S. cerevisiae*, *S. pombe*, and *A. thaliana*. There is an individual ontology for each of the supported organisms. There is also an integrated ontology additionally containing (putative) orthology relationships, obtained through OrthoMCL clustering. Currently, the integrated CCO contains 65 437 terms: 33 610 proteins (including their modified forms), 10 739 genes, and 27 297 protein-protein interactions, and it further comprises 30 types of relationships (properties) (see Tables 1-3 for detailed information). The contents of CCO can be viewed and analysed through a wide variety of tools (see below).

Main features of CCO

CCO is protein centric, meaning that proteins are used as “hubs” to integrate and connect knowledge. The semantic integration of knowledge creates synergy by allowing queries that are not otherwise possible. For

example, OBO ontologies can be queried by tools such as OBO-Edit [62], the OBO Explorer [58], and AmiGO [63], but none of these can deal with a query like “return the orthologs of a protein X and include all the biological processes and molecular functions in which these orthologs participate”. Due to our integrative approach and selection of information sources, CCO is an information-rich ontology, offering many advantages for cell cycle researchers. The main characteristics and functionalities of CCO, described in more detail below, can best be summarised as follows:

- integrated turnkey system: CCO evolves toward a one-stop shop for cell cycle researchers;
- exploratory analysis: the system provides ample possibilities for browsing, visualising and searching;
- querying facilities: the application offers advanced methods to retrieve data;
- reasoning exploitation: the integrated knowledge is structured to allow classification, consistency checking, and more advanced implementations that may provide new hypotheses.

CCO is made available in a wide range of formats to accommodate a suite of popular visualisation and analysis tools, ensuring maximum flexibility of interaction with the ontology: OBOF, OWL [64], RDF [65], eXtensible Markup Language (XML) [66], DOT [67] and Graph Modelling Language (GML) [68]. Those formats can be classified in three groups, according to the way the user interacts with CCO: a basic exploration of the structure (OBOF); expressive queries including the possibility to combine CCO with other resources (XML, RDF and OWL); and visual exploration (GML, XML –visANT [69]– and DOT). The representations are described in detail as follows:

1. OBOF, the *de facto* standard for knowledge representation in the bio-ontology community. Many tools have been built to accommodate OBOF (*e.g.* OBO-Edit [50] and OBO Explorer [58]), and they are widely used by biologists. Much of the biological knowledge already captured in ontologies is represented in OBOF [70]. This is why we chose the OBOF resource as the starting point for the CCO pipeline. The OBOF version of CCO is compliant with version 1.2 of the OBOF specification. OBOF, however, offers little in the way of native reasoning services and even lacks a semantic infrastructure for knowledge integration, like RDF and OWL do via Uniform Resource Identifiers (URIs). OBOF queries are limited to simple exploration of the ontology structure.
2. An RDF model is a collection of triple patterns, also simply named ‘triples’, comprising a subject, a predicate and an object (see Figure 4) connected to each other in a graph (for example, the subject

of one triple can be the object of another triple). An RDF graph can be flexibly and efficiently queried with the graph query language SPARQL [71] (Figure 5). We have loaded the RDF version of CCO into Open Virtuoso [72] to enable complex queries via SPARQL. In addition, an SPARQL query form (<http://www.cellcycleontology.org/query/sparql>), and an SPARQL query service (<http://crunch.fvms.ugent.be:8890/sparql>) are also available to exploit CCO. The CCO RDF allows a first step toward exploiting Semantic Web technologies [73], as it offers the possibility to integrate knowledge from external resources [74]. Tools like RDFScope [75] (a plug-in for Cytoscape [76]) can also be used to explore this CCO representation.

3. The OWL version of CCO is the most expressive and exceeds the other versions in information content as new axioms (see Materials and Methods) have been added to exploit the language capabilities (the other versions are equivalent in content to the original ontologies in OBOF). OWL also allows integration of other ontologies within CCO by using an importing mechanism based on URIs, meaning that extant encoded knowledge from other resources can be effectively added and exploited. Ontologies expressed in OWL, however, often cause performance limitations to the extent that it is prohibitive for specific tools, such as Protégé, when launching very complex queries. OWL reasoners (Pellet [77], FaCT++ [78], RACERPro [79], and KAON2 [80]) can have problems in dealing with large ontologies (such as CCO) and sometimes fail without explanation [81]. Additionally, the OWLDoc server [82] allows online queries over CCO (<http://www.cellcycleontology.org/query/owl-dl>).
4. XML allows efficient data processing and programmatic access to the ontology. XML has less expressivity than RDF or OWL in terms of semantics. The structured document enabled in XML also supports querying (for example, with technologies such as XQuery [83]).
5. GML, XML (visANT), and DOT allow visual exploration of CCO by tools such as Cytoscape [76], visANT, and Graphviz [84]. visANT, in particular, provides a very user-friendly way to examine the CCO network of terms and relationships.

Querying the CCO with SPARQL

The SPARQL syntax is based on the triple pattern of RDF and, therefore, allows a detailed specification of a small graph, thus a collection of interconnected triples, for which the graph should be queried. When performing a query with SPARQL, a small RDF graph is built in which any of the elements of any triple

can be a variable (variable names are prepended in the query with the sign ? or \$). This query graph is used to match against the complete RDF graph and any matching structure (collection of triples) is retrieved (Figure 5).

A query can also specify which variables from the retrieved triples (subject, predicate, or object) should be shown in the answer. A strong point of SPARQL is its ability to specify various target graphs that could be used in the same query, resulting in their subsequent combination and effectively constituting an efficient data integration mechanism. As the pointers to the graphs are URIs, knowledge represented in dispersed RDF resources can be combined in a powerful way.

In order to design SPARQL queries on CCO, it is sometimes necessary to deal with CCO identifiers. The following query shows how to retrieve a term name (called “label” in RDF) corresponding to a given CCO identifier (“CCO_B0000000” in this example). First, a base URL is defined (BASE), then the prefixes (PREFIX) are set to define which graphs should be used in the query. Finally, the variables (columns) to be shown in the solution are specified (SELECT statement) followed by a description of the subgraph to be used for matching the target graph (WHERE block). The result table will display the term label: “core cell cycle protein”.

```
BASE <http://www.cellcycleontology.org/ontology/rdf/>
PREFIX rdfs:<http://www.w3.org/2000/01/rdf-schema#>
PREFIX cco:<http://www.cellcycleontology.org/ontology/rdf/CCO#>
SELECT ?term_label
WHERE {
    cco:CCO_B0000000 rdfs:label ?term_label.
}
```

A similar query can be employed to retrieve a CCO identifier using a term label. The following query fetches the CCO identifier (“CCO_B0002337”) of the protein with the label “WEE1_ARATH”:

```
BASE <http://www.cellcycleontology.org/ontology/rdf/>
PREFIX rdfs:<http://www.w3.org/2000/01/rdf-schema#>
SELECT ?unique_id
WHERE {
    GRAPH <CCO> {
```

```

        ?unique_id rdfs:label "WEE1_ARATH"@en
    }
}

```

More sophisticated searches based on regular expressions can also be performed as illustrated in the following query that retrieves all the terms having the word “meiosis” anywhere within the label:

```

BASE <http://www.cellcycleontology.org/ontology/rdf/>
PREFIX rdfs:<http://www.w3.org/2000/01/rdf-schema#>
PREFIX cco:<http://www.cellcycleontology.org/ontology/rdf/CCO#>
SELECT ?unique_id ?name
WHERE {
    GRAPH <CCO> {
        ?unique_id rdfs:label ?name.
        FILTER regex(str(?name), 'meiosis').
    }
}

```

Consider the simple query “retrieve the names (labels) of all core cell cycle proteins from *S. pombe*”. These are the proteins annotated with cell cycle terms by the Gene Ontology Annotation (GOA) [85] group. The subgraph that represents this query consists of two triples. The first triple will match any triple that relates any subject through the “is-a” predicate to the “CCO_B0000000” object (core cell cycle protein) and the second triple will match any triple whose subject is the same as in the first triple, the variable ?protein (defined by ? or \$ in front of a string name), and has the predicate “rdfs:label” pointing to any object. The result is a column (?protein_label) with the label of 747 core cell cycle proteins in *S. pombe* (e.g. CDC24_SCHPO). Figure 5 illustrates the defined subgraph and the corresponding SPARQL query is:

```

PREFIX rdfs:<http://www.w3.org/2000/01/rdf-schema#>
PREFIX sp:<http://www.cellcycleontology.org/ontology/rdf/Sp#>
SELECT ?protein_label
FROM <http://www.cellcycleontology.org/ontology/rdf/Sp#>
WHERE {
    ?protein sp:is_a sp:CCO_B0000000.
}

```

```

    ?protein rdfs:label ?protein_label
}

```

The following SPARQL query on the *A. thaliana* graph allows users to infer a putative location for proteins with no documented cellular locations. The assumption behind such a query is that two proteins that participate in the same interaction are likely to share the same cellular location, *e.g.* the “nucleus” (CCO_C0000252):

```

PREFIX rdfs:<http://www.w3.org/2000/01/rdf-schema#>
PREFIX at:<http://www.cellcycleontology.org/ontology/rdf/At#>
SELECT
    ?prot_in_the_nucleus
    ?prot_to_study
    ?interaction_label
FROM <http://www.cellcycleontology.org/ontology/rdf/At#>
WHERE {
    ?interaction rdf:type at:interaction.
    ?interaction rdfs:label ?interaction_label.
    ?prot_A at:participates_in ?interaction.
    ?prot_B at:participates_in ?interaction.
    ?prot_A rdfs:label ?prot_in_the_nucleus.
    ?prot_B rdfs:label ?prot_to_study.
    ?prot_A at:located_in at:CCO_C0000252.
    optional {
        ?prot_B at:located_in ?location_B.
    }
    FILTER (!bound(?location_B))
}

```

The query returns 38 proteins (*e.g.* DMC1_ARATH, SEM12_ARATH) having an interaction with a documented nuclear protein, meaning their own cellular location is also likely to include “nucleus” at some point. These results and, more generally, any answer to a query on CCO simply reflects the information in

the original sources, but their integration enables the construction of new hypotheses.

For some questions the integrated CCO graph must be used. For instance, to retrieve the orthologs of the protein TIP41_SCHPO from *S. pombe* (CCO_B0001243) and the processes in which these orthologs participate, the following query can be used:

```
PREFIX rdfs:<http://www.w3.org/2000/01/rdf-schema#>
PREFIX cco:<http://www.cellcycleontology.org/ontology/rdf/CCO#>
SELECT
    ?prot_label
    ?biological_process_label
FROM <http://www.cellcycleontology.org/ontology/rdf/CCO>
WHERE {
    cco:CCO_B0001243 cco:is_a ?ortholog_cluster_protein.
    ?prot cco:is_a ?ortholog_cluster_protein.
    ?prot rdfs:label ?prot_label.
    ?ortholog_cluster_protein rdf:type cco:type_protein.
OPTIONAL {
    ?prot cco:participates_in ?biological_process.
    ?biological_process rdfs:label ?biological_process_label
}
FILTER(?prot != cco:CCO_B0001243)
}
```

The query returns two putative orthologs: TIPRL_HUMAN (CCO_B0018958) and A6ZWT2_YEAS7 (CCO_B0032729), neither of which is documented to participate in any known process. Thus, with this result, these proteins can be hypothesised to participate in the same process as TIP41_SCHPO. To retrieve the identity of the processes in which TIP41_SCHPO participates, a new query must be built that returns the answer “G2/M transition of mitotic cell cycle”:

```
PREFIX rdfs:<http://www.w3.org/2000/01/rdf-schema#>
PREFIX cco:<http://www.cellcycleontology.org/ontology/rdf/CCO#>
SELECT ?process_label
```

```

FROM <http://www.cellcycleontology.org/ontology/rdf/CCO>
WHERE {
    cco:CCO_B0001243 cco:participates_in ?process.
    ?process rdfs:label ?process_label
}

```

More examples of biological queries can be found at <http://www.cellcycleontology.org/query/sparql>.

Finally, we used SPARQL to analyse the sub-cellular distribution of cell cycle proteins. For that we used the core cell cycle proteins subset of the CCO. First, we analysed the distribution among the three major cellular compartments—the cytoplasm, nucleus and cell membrane. We found that the majority of cell cycle proteins are located in the nucleus (755) and the cytoplasm (356), where the majority of cell cycle events are known to take place [38]. 25 cell cycle proteins were found to be located in the cell membrane; these are likely to play a role in signalling to the cell cycle machinery.

We looked in more detail at the distribution of cell cycle proteins in the cytoplasm. As expected, the majority of cell cycle proteins are found in the cytosol (280). We also wanted to see if there were cell cycle proteins in the membrane bounded organelles other than the nucleus. To our surprise, all of the analysed organelles contained cell cycle proteins: the endoplasmic reticulum (46), the Golgi apparatus (19) and the mitochondrion (43). One could hypothesise that the cell cycle proteins located in the first two compartments are involved in the build up of a new cell membrane and cell wall between the two daughter cells. It is, however, much more difficult to envision how mitochondrial proteins could be involved in the cell cycle. Even more strikingly, 6 mitochondrial proteins were found to play a role in the regulation of the cell cycle. Provided the cellular compartment annotations are correct, these results, if taken up by cell cycle researchers, may possibly lead to the discovery of novel mechanisms of cell cycle regulation.

An alternative hypothesis to explain a cell cycle role for proteins known to be located in membrane bounded organelles other than the nucleus is to suggest that these proteins are also present outside of those organelles. For example, if a protein can be located both in the mitochondrion and the cytosol, then the cell cycle function of the protein can be exerted in the cytosol, but not in the mitochondrion where it may fulfil a different role. Therefore, we analysed alternative locations of the proteins in question. We identified 9, 5 and 15 core cell cycle proteins from the endoplasmic reticulum, Golgi apparatus and mitochondrion, respectively, that have additionally cytosolic or nuclear localisation. These proteins have an unusual

combination of locations and merit further investigation with respect to the molecular mechanisms underlying their ability to be localised to apparently incompatible locations. This also highlights the need to indicate when and where functions assigned to a protein are valid.

Automated Reasoning over Bio-ontologies

Description Logics and Automated reasoners

Description Logics (DL) [86] and Semantic Web technologies [60] provide a foundation for the management and exploitation of knowledge in ontologies. The type of OWL used for CCO is based on DL, which is a family of logic-based knowledge representation formalisms that describe a domain in terms of concepts (classes), roles (properties or relationships) and individuals (instances). OWL-DL offers an optimal trade-off between expressivity and computational tractability [86]. OWL-DL can be considered sufficiently expressive to represent a wide variety of biomedical knowledge [87], while it offers support for automated reasoning. It has become a standard language for representing ontologies in the semantically strict form that supports automated reasoning.

DL reasoners are computational tools to:

1. ensure that an ontology does not contain any contradictory facts (*consistency checking*);
2. compute the subclass relation between each named class to create the class hierarchy (*classification*);
3. find the most specific classes to which an individual belongs (*realization*); and
4. retrieve information from an ontology (*querying*).

Ontology curators can use DL reasoners to minimise the term redundancy, while maintaining sufficiently detailed descriptions and consistency of the contents [18,19]. Moreover, reasoning tools can also be used to find new classes (either more specific or general) [20]. Finally, and in this context most importantly, reasoning tools can also be used in biological research, for information retrieval and generation of new hypotheses that are consistent with the knowledge captured in the ontology.

Representing biological knowledge with OWL

OWL-DL queries can be more fine-grained than RDF queries since the semantic model of OWL-DL allows more expressivity. The OWL semantics is based on sets (classes) of instances (individuals). Classes can be subclasses of other classes, if and only if all the instances of the subclass are also instances of the

superclass, but the superclass has other instances that do not belong to the subclass. In GO, for example, the well-known “is a” hierarchy is founded on this concept.

Relationships in OWL-DL are interpreted as existing between pairs of individuals. Restrictions on classes define which and how many relationships the instances of that class must hold. When a restriction is defined, an anonymous class is defined (Figure 6, dotted shape) and the class to which the restriction is added becomes a subclass or equivalent class of that anonymous class. For example, the restriction “subClassOf part of some Cell” in the class “Nucleus” states that every instance of the class “Nucleus” must have at least one relationship along the property “part of” to an instance of the class “Cell” (Other quantifiers can be used in these restrictions, such as “only”, “min”, “max” and “value”, and Boolean operators like “and”, “or”, and “not”).

If the restriction is added as a superclass of the class that is being defined (the class being defined is a subclass of the restriction, as in the example above), the restriction is known as a *necessary* condition. A necessary condition is a condition that all the instances of the class *must* fulfil, but it is not enough in itself to *define* class membership. Therefore, if an instance is found that has at least one “part of” relationship to “Cell”, it does not mean that it is a member of the class “Nucleus”. If a restriction is added as an equivalent class of the class that is being described, then this restriction is known as a *necessary and sufficient* condition (if an instance with at least one “part of Cell” relationship is found, it is a member of the class “Nucleus”). Restrictions can also be composed and nested, such as “part of some (participates in only (mitosis or meiosis))”, providing a powerful mechanism for expressing complex conditions.

OWL works under the Open World Assumption (OWA), in which something not known to be true is not assumed to be false, but merely to be “unknown”. This is in contrast to database management systems (DBMS) that work with the Closed World Assumption (CWA). In DBMS, anything that is not demonstrated by the stored data to be true is assumed to be false. As an example, let us assume that in a system the following and only the following is stated: “protein CDC25_YEAST participates in the regulation of the cell cycle process”, and if the query: “does protein CDC25_YEAST participate in the regulation of spindle elongation?” is asked, the answer will depend on the type of system. In a CWA-based system (*e.g.* a typical DBMS), the answer will be “no” whereas in an OWA-based system (*e.g.* an OWL knowledge base) the answer will be “unknown”; in other words, protein CDC25 YEAST might also participate in other processes, and will remain “unknown” until it is explicitly stated that it either does or

does not participate in that process. The OWA model complies well with the Semantic Web vision, where knowledge is continuously evolving, and efficiently accommodates domains with incomplete knowledge such as the cell cycle.

In an OWL ontology, the knowledge is asserted by the user, and the reasoner makes the axioms that are implicit in such asserted knowledge explicit, therefore inferring axioms that flag unnoticed items of knowledge. Therefore, the complexity of OWL queries depends on the complexity of the asserted and inferred knowledge present on the ontology. An OWL query can be regarded as an “anonymous class” and, therefore, the user may ask the reasoner for different answers (*e.g.* retrieve superclasses, ancestor classes, equivalent classes, subclasses, descendant classes, or instances of the anonymous class). CCO provides an attractive starting point to exploit all these querying possibilities by enriching it with particular/customised axioms. These axioms could be limited to subsets of CCO to enable focusing on a particular aspect of cell cycle research (such as endoreduplication). The examples described below only show some of the added value that could be gained from having an ontology expressed in OWL.

Examples of automated reasoning in the CCO

Consider the simple query: “Which cell cycle related proteins participate in a reported interaction?” In the Manchester OWL syntax [88], that query would be:

```
protein and
participates_in some 'interaction type'
```

where the classes “protein” and “interaction type” have respectively CCO_U0000005 and CCO_Y0000001 as their CCO identifiers. When the query is launched, an anonymous class is built on the fly. The extension of that anonymous class is the set of individuals that are members of the class “protein” with at least one relationship (due to the “some” keyword) along the property “participates in” to an individual of the class “interaction type”. The expressions to create an anonymous class can be of arbitrary complexity: combination of constructors, nested expressions, combinations of different types of restrictions, *etc.* For example, if we want to know which proteins (CCO_U0000005) participate in the “mitosis” (CCO_P0000081) or any process that is a part of it, we may use the expression below, which shows the versatility and power of OWL expressions:

```
protein and
```

```

participates_in some (
    mitosis or part_of some mitosis
)

```

The extension of this anonymous class is the set of instances that are members of the class “protein” (CCO_U0000005) and have at least one relationship along “participates_in” to an individual of the class “mitosis” (CCO_P0000081) or to an individual that has itself at least one relationship along “part_of” to an individual of “mitosis”. Reasoning is used to exploit the transitivity of the “part_of” and subsumption relationships. Thus, *e.g.* a process that is not directly part of mitosis, but it is part of a process that it is part of mitosis, will be taken into account, even though such knowledge is not asserted in the ontology: such knowledge is inferred by the reasoner, and it is implicit (asserted) in the axioms of the ontology.

Another example is retrieving proteins that have at least one interaction with other proteins and can be located in the cytoplasm as well as in the nucleus:

```

protein and
participates_in some interaction and
((located_in some (part_of some cytoplasm)) or (located_in some cytoplasm)) and
((located_in some (part_of some nucleus)) or (located_in some nucleus))

```

This query defines an anonymous class formed by “proteins” (CCO_U0000005) that participate in at least one “interaction” (CCO_U0000007) and are located in the “cytoplasm” (CCO_C0000323) or any part of it and the “nucleus” (CCO_C0000251) or any part of it.

As another example, let us consider the query that defines an anonymous class formed by the entities that are the location of proteins participating in the “S phase” (CCO_P0000014) or any process that is part of it. This query returns 13 proteins for *H. sapiens*, such as “microtubule organising center” (CCO_C0000385), which is the location of the protein CHM1A.HUMAN that participates in negative regulation of the S phase of the mitotic cell cycle (part of the S phase in mitotic cell cycle):

```

location_of some (
    participates_in some (
        'S phase' or (part_of some 'S phase')
    )
)

```

)

The same procedure can be applied to any defined query with the OWL-DL query service provided by Protégé 4, and also programmatically via the OWL application programming interface (OWL-API) [89].

The OWL-DL version of CCO constitutes a structured and integrated knowledge framework that may serve as a basis for advanced reasoning approaches. Reasoning services can be applied to CCO at different levels, depending on who interacts with the system (such as a molecular biologist, or an ontology specialist [90,91]), to check the consistency of knowledge, to validate cell cycle related hypotheses and to make implicit knowledge explicit.

CCO integrated into a platform for Cell Cycle research

The querying and analysis of results of SPARQL queries can be intimidating for lay users. We therefore set out to build a visualiser of biological networks specifically for CCO (in the framework of the EU FP6 project DIAMONDS, <http://www.SBcellcycle.org>). This visualiser is a JAVA applet that shows a screen consisting of two parts (Figure 7): one section with a panel where applet functionalities are grouped and can be configured, and another panel with a graphical representation of results of queries (usually in the form of networks) to CCO. SPARQL provides intuitive ways to query hierarchical networks. With a right click of the mouse on any of the nodes shown by the applet, the user can ask for the local neighbourhood of a term in the network, for the path to the root and for extra information like definitions and synonyms. Users can see the networks, personalise them, add or delete elements, change colours, and move and re-design the shape of the networks.

The terms in CCO are basically divided into three types:

1. terms that represent a protein class (like 'UBC11_SCHPO'),
2. terms in the upper level ontology (like 'biological process'),
3. other ontological terms (like 'nucleolus').

The RDF contains explicit "rdf:type" links from every term node to its type, as well as "rdfs:label" links to their names. All the pre-defined SPARQL queries operate on the Unique Resource Identifiers (URIs) of the CCO terms, but they retrieve the "rdf:type" and "rdfs:label" for the visual presentation of the results. The types are used for a colour coding of the nodes. The links between the terms also have names, defined by

the relation types in CCO (*e.g.* interacts with, encoded by, *etc.*). Some of the relation types, like the protein interactions, are visualised with special arrows. For more information, please see the DIAMONDS deliverable D5.4 (http://www.sbcellcycle.org/Deliverables/D5.4_FINAL_PRODUCT.pdf)

Yet another integrated system?

Efficient use of biological information that is in practice widely dispersed strongly relies on its means of access. Each individual resource, however, mostly informs the researchers about only a part of their biological question. Therefore, life scientists often need to combine several resources in order to gain new insights. Computational systems that provide a transparent and integrative access should increase research productivity. Some systems, such as Reactome [92] and PANTHER [93], are examples of developments in that direction. These systems are, however, not so easily expandable to include other domains or information on-the-fly or upon request. More importantly, although those systems provide highly curated information and user-friendly interfaces, the information retrieval is still limited to simple search forms that only allow keyword-based look ups. The possibilities to use the stored information through complex, but more specific and informative queries, remains limited. Also, these systems lack means to make implicit knowledge explicit; this is where the reasoning services available in CCO offer added value.

CCO adapts a data integration paradigm that can be readily applied to any other domain. The system is readily expandable and can accommodate virtually any other data related to the cell cycle (*e.g.* cell cycle related information from KEGG [94] and OMIM [95]). Furthermore, the use of Semantic Web technologies in CCO enables interoperability with other Semantic Web resources and constitutes a step towards a universal, interoperable knowledge architecture [96] for the life sciences. Semantic web integration alleviates the burden of resource maintenance, allowing more attention to local improvements (as shown with the reasoning cases in CCO). A universal and interoperable knowledge-based approach can enable implementation of an effective integrated biology.

Building complex queries over CCO may currently require some training in semantic technologies. It has always been difficult to develop systems providing a balanced trade-off between user-friendliness and the possibility of asking complex questions. Nevertheless, it is fair to assume that Semantic Web research will deliver such features in the future. The rich ontology developed to study the cell cycle process highlights the advantages of semantically representing knowledge for further analysis and ontology-driven hypothesis generation. We envision that by improving both contents and semantics the utility of CCO can be

considerably increased.

Materials and Methods

Data integration pipeline

CCO is built from scratch every two months, only the identifiers are kept for consistency between releases. This automatic pipeline encompasses the typical life cycle of an integrated system: set-up, data integration, and system maintenance. All the integrated information is cross-referenced to the original sources to ensure data provenance. The integration pipeline relies on the ability to programmatically manipulate ontologies, terms and relations, a functionality offered by ONTO-PERL [57]. The code of the pipeline is available as supplementary material. The output of the pipeline is four species-specific ontologies plus a composite ontology that integrates the species-specific ontologies via orthology relationships. Figure 2 depicts the system integration pipeline and the different phases of its development.

Set-up

In this initial phase, the ontology structure and its lexicon (for formal ontology definitions, see [97]) are created. The core CCO ontology is built from the Upper Level Ontology (ULO, see below) and the latest releases of GO, RO, MI [98] and NCBI taxonomy, in the order specified.

Initially, a “pre-cell cycle ontology” is built that constitutes the backbone for the CCO ontologies (the four species-specific ontologies and the integrated ontology). The main data source used for CCO is GO. From the “biological processes” subontology of GO, the complete branch under the term “cell cycle” (GO:0007049) with all its descendants is imported (“pre-cell cycle ontology”). We refer to the terms contained in this branch as ‘cell cycle’ terms. Currently, 378 cell cycle biological processes are imported from the GO. The entire “cellular component” and “molecular function” subontologies are imported. Every entity within CCO is given a unique identifier of the form CCO:Xnnnnnnn where “CCO” represents the ontology namespace, “X” the entity subnamespace, and “nnnnnnn” a sequence of seven digits. The legal subnamespaces include: “C” for cellular components, “P” for biological processes, “F” for molecular functions, “B” for proteins, “G” for genes, “T” for taxon terms, “I” for interactions, “O” for orthology terms, “Y” for interaction types, and “U” for upper level ontology terms. All the original identifiers of the imported terms are stored in the ‘xref’ section. Additionally, an association table keeps track of the mapping between GO identifiers and CCO identifiers.

Next, the RO is fully incorporated and the ‘interaction type’ branch from the MI is integrated. Then, a

specific taxonomy is built on the basis of the NCBI taxonomy for *H. sapiens*, *S. cerevisiae*, *S. pombe*, and *A. thaliana*.

Data integration

The integration follows a protein centric model in which the proteins are considered as integration pivots that connect their relevant data (such as the molecular functions in which they participate).

The proteins defined as the “core cell cycle proteins” above are added to CCO as the children of the term ‘core cell cycle protein’ (CCO:B0000000) and used as the starting point (seed) for the data integration process. Currently, CCO has 602 “core cell cycle” proteins for *S. cerevisiae*, 162 for *A. thaliana*, 749 for *S. pombe*, and 870 for *H. sapiens* (Table 2).

Following this, all the proteins annotated with cell cycle terms in the corresponding Gene Ontology Association (GOA) files [99] are added to form the “core cell cycle” protein section of CCO. This section is then expanded to include the proteins known to interact with the core cell cycle proteins, as documented in IntAct (only one degree of separation). The protein role (prey, bait, or neutral component), type of experiment (such as yeast two hybrid), type of interaction (such as physical association), *etc.* are all retained in CCO. Then, protein information (such as synonym names, encoding genes, and cross references) are fetched from the UniProt knowledge base. In addition, post-translational modification data, when available in UniProt, is also added by creating new terms defined by their specific modification. Finally, the OrthoMCL clustering utility is used to generate clusters of putative orthologs for the four species included in the CCO. The parameters used for running OrthoMCL have been chosen to obtain a balanced size of the resulting clusters. Compared to the default values, the following parameters were changed to make the clusters more homogeneous: $pv_cutoff = 1e-6$, $pi_cutoff = 25$, $inflation = 4$. The input all-against-all BLAST matrix for the four complete proteomes is produced with the Tera-BLAST hardware implementation of BLAST (<http://www.timelogic.com>) with default parameter settings. All the proteins classified by OrthoMCL as orthologous to the core cell cycle proteins are incorporated (along with their corresponding genes and other protein information) into the integrated CCO ontology (Table 3). In this way the orthology data glued the four specific ontologies together by adding cluster types to which the proteins of the different species belong.

All the imported entries from the sources are cross-referenced via ‘xref’ tags so that the data can be tracked back to its source. Finally, the four organism-specific ontologies and the CCO composite ontology (output

of this phase) are checked and made available, effectively producing the official release of the system.

All the entities in CCO (proteins-including their modified forms, genes, interactions, *etc.*) are modelled as classes (also known as universals [100]) since they gather shared commonalities which are present in all the particulars (instances) they represent. Some of the formal ontology design principles as specified by OBOF have been relaxed while building CCO. For instance, it is evident that the simple sample fact represented by a relationship between a given protein P and a particular location L (“P located in L”) can be read as: “all proteins of type P are located in L” or “some of proteins of type P are located in L”. Actually, the best interpretation of GOA annotations could be ‘some of P **may** be located in L’. What is the case depends on a particular cell type, particular timing (in the development or cell cycle) and so on. Therefore, such statements should be considered carefully while performing the analysis [101,102].

System maintenance

Semantic improvements are incorporated in this phase, further enriching the ontology (see section Improving the OWL version of the CCO).

Validation and verification processes are carried out while building CCO to ensure its soundness. The ontologies generated in the previous phase are manually and automatically checked by ontology editors, validators and reasoners. In addition, the pipeline log execution files are inspected in detail. These files are sufficiently detailed to point out any possible problems. This has allowed us to assemble a fully automated pipeline that uploads the ontologies and their exports in the different formats to the CCO website and to all related and supporting repositories:

1. CCO Website: <http://www.cellcycleontology.org/>
2. FTP site: <ftp://ftp.psb.ugent.be/pub/cco/ontology/>
3. BioPortal: <http://bioportal.bioontology.org/>
4. OLS: <http://www.ebi.ac.uk/ontology-lookup/>
5. SVN repository: <http://cellcycleonto.svn.sourceforge.net/viewvc/cellcycleonto/ONTOLOGIES>
6. CVS repository: <http://cellcycleonto.cvs.sourceforge.net/cellcycleonto/ONTOLOGIES>

For each release, the whole set of sources (ontologies, databases, etc) are fetched from their repositories. Therefore, CCO is a dynamic artefact in which the terms and relationships are updated as new data are

released. Versioning servers keep track of all the changes between different releases.

An Upper Level Ontology for application ontologies in life sciences

An Upper Level Ontology (ULO) is an ontology that structures very general types of concepts (such as a process) in generic as well as specific domains [103] to provide an integration scaffold for including other ontologies. A ULO connects a relatively small number of concepts by meaningful and strictly defined relationships. To accommodate natural interlinkage of terms and relationships for cell cycle knowledge, we developed a ULO for CCO (Figure 3). The implementation of this ULO was based on some of the concepts presented in the Basic Formal Ontology (BFO) [104, 105] to ensure interoperability of CCO with other ontologies. Our ULO has been customised for CCO by inclusion of a few high-level terms, such as 'cell cycle gene'. The developed ULO is generic and can also serve other subdomains of life sciences (*e.g.* programmed cell death), with minor modifications.

Improving the OWL version of the CCO

The Ontology Pre-Processor Language (OPPL) [106, 107] is a language for manipulating OWL ontologies. OPPL is based on the Manchester OWL Syntax, and it is used to write macros to be applied to an OWL ontology. The OPPL macros are written by the user in a flat file that is processed by the OPPL program that executes the instructions and generates a new ontology. OPPL macros can be used to add or remove entities and axioms (for instance, **subClassOf part_of some all (participates_in only (process and interaction))**). In the example below a sample definition of axioms or transformations on the CCO are made with OPPL (statements end with semicolon, and comments (not processed) start with hash):

```
# Add a class called "interaction".
# Add the following necessary condition to the newly added "interaction" class:
# the participants are only the union of protein_1 and protein_2.
# Add the rdfs:label "interaction" to the newly added "interaction" class.
ADD Class interaction;
ADD subClassOf has_participant only (protein_1 or protein_2);
ADD label "interaction";
# Select any class that has the following condition as a superclass:
# the participants are only the union of protein_1 and protein_2.
# Remove the rdfs:label "interaction" from any selected class.
```

```
# Add the rdfs:label "interaction of protein_1 and protein_2" to any selected class.  
SELECT subClassOf has_participant only (protein_1 or protein_2);  
REMOVE label "interaction";  
ADD label "interaction of protein_1 and protein_2";
```

OPPL is used to enrich the OWL ontology that the CCO pipeline builds from the original OBOF files. The advantages of OPPL are automatic maintenance, and consistent, explicit and flexible development. OPPL has also the capability of performing that would be otherwise prohibitive using a graphical interface=. The set of axioms used to enrich CCO via OPPL can be found in <http://www.cellcycleontology.org/download/supplementary-files>.

OPPL has been also used to apply Ontology Design Patterns (ODPs) in CCO [108,109]. ODPs are ready-made modelling solutions for ontologies, thoroughly tested and documented, offering an abstraction to be reused in different implementations. The abstraction also means that a developer need not know all the modelling details and can use the ODPs as self-sufficient modelling components. Within CCO, two ODPs were used: the Sequence ODP [110] and the Upper Level Ontology ODP [111].

List of abbreviations used

- API: Application programming interface
- BFO: Basic Formal Ontology
- CCO: Cell Cycle Ontology
- CWA: Closed World Assumption
- DBMS: Database Management Systems
- DL: Description Logics
- GML: Graph Modelling Language
- GO: Gene Ontology
- GOA: Gene Ontology Annotation
- MeSH: Medical Subject Headings
- MI: Molecular Interactions ontology

- NCBI: National Center for Biotechnology Information
- OBO: Open Biomedical Ontology
- OBOF: Open Biomedical Ontology Format
- ODP: Ontology Design Pattern
- OPPL: Ontology Pre-Processor Language
- OWA: Open World Assumption
- OWL: Web Ontology Language
- RDF: Resource Description Framework
- RO: Relation Ontology
- SPARQL: SPARQL Protocol and RDF Query Language
- ULO: Upper Level Ontology
- URI: Uniform Resource Identifier
- XML: eXtensible Markup Language

Authors contributions

EA was the main driving architect and engineer of CCO. ME contributed expertise in bio-ontologies, ODPs and OPPL. VM contributed cell cycle expertise and ontology design. RS provided bio-ontologies expertise. WB contributed building some queries and setting up the DIAMONDS platform. BDB and MTRK contributed with their expertise about knowledge management in systems biology and steered the project.

Availability

The Cell Cycle Ontology is available at <http://www.cellcycleontology.org> and at <https://sourceforge.net/projects/cellcycleonto/> (both through CVS and SVN). An interactive SPARQL query interface is available at <http://www.cellcycleontology.org/query/sparql>. CCO can also be browsed, searched, and visualised with the BioPortal at <http://bioportal.bioontology.org/> (hosted at the NCBO) facilities and is also available at The Ontology Lookup Service (OLS) [112] at

<http://www.ebi.ac.uk/ontology-lookup/> that allows interactions with other systems through a SOAP interface. Comments and suggestions about CCO can be exchanged through a mailing list (ccofriends@psb.ugent.be).

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Figures

Figure 1 - Local neighbourhood of the SWI4_YEAST protein.

Example of the local neighbourhood of the protein SWI4_YEAST: some of the types of relationships used within CCO depict how a given protein (SWI4_YEAST) is connected to the organism it belongs to (*S. cerevisiae*), its coding gene (SWI4_yeast), biological processes (G1/S transition of mitotic cell cycle), cellular localisation (nucleus), interactions (physical interactions), protein transformations (post-translational modifications), and its orthology group.

Figure 2 - CCO Pipeline

The CCO data integration pipeline scheme plots the principal phases: set-up, data integration and system's life cycle. In the first phase, several existing ontologies are integrated and merged: the Gene Ontology, the Relations Ontology, the Molecular Interactions ontology, an Upper Level Ontology (see Section) and an ontology holding taxonomical terms for the four model organisms supported by CCO (*A. thaliana*, *H. sapiens*, *S. cerevisiae*, and *S. pombe*). A core cell cycle ontology is generated as output from this initial phase which in turn serves as input for the data integration phase where GOA annotations and protein data, such as protein-protein interactions, are integrated. Finally, life cycle phase depicts the maintenance of the system by considering the stages of updating the integrated data (such as ontologies, protein data). This phase also shows the generation (export) in different formats for further exploitation.

Figure 3 - Upper Level Ontology for CCO

Upper Level Ontology (ULO) for CCO. It provides a hierarchical scaffold including generic terms (*e.g.* cell cycle gene) which serve as “hooks” for hanging the integrated resources. The dashed rectangles represent the type of data residing below the parental nodes: the node called “Data from GO” under the term “cellular component” shows the placeholder where the cellular components from GO are placed

(*e.g.* nucleus), the node “Data from UniProt” under the term “protein” shows the placeholder where protein data from UniProt resides (*e.g.* p53), and so forth.

Figure 4 - RDF triple sample

Simple RDF triple sample showing the subject (Nucleus), the predicate (part_of), and the object (Cell).

Figure 5 - RDF matching model

RDF matching model: while querying an RDF model, a matching process is performed against the graph model. In the sample, the triples “?protein is_a CCO_B0000000” and “?protein rdfs:label ?protein label” are matched against the graph on the left.

Figure 6 - OWL property (part_of) sample

OWL property (part_of) sample: the property “part of” links individuals belonging to a class (*e.g.* “Nucleus”) to individuals of the class “Cell”. A restriction of the type “some part_of Cell” on the class “Nucleus” defines an anonymous class (dotted shape) and it will imply that individuals belonging to the class “Nucleus” also belong to (are “part_of”) the class “Cell”.

Figure 7 - CCO visualisation applet

The CCO-terms are shown as clickable, colour-coded nodes, and mouse actions of the user are translated into pre-defined SPARQL queries that operate on the RDF representation of CCO. The results are returned as an XML file, which is translated into new nodes and edges that are then shown in the display. This visualisation sample shows the local neighbourhood of the protein WEE1_SCHPO (“Mitosis inhibitor protein kinase wee1”).

Tables

Table 1 - Organism-specific ontology figures

The numbers are shown of some important entities presently contained in CCO (*e.g.* cell cycle genes) for each of the organism-specific ontologies (*A. thaliana* ontology [At], *H. sapiens* ontology [Hs], *S. cerevisiae* ontology [Sc], and *S. pombe* ontology [Sp]).

Entity	Ontology			
	At	Hs	Sc	Sp
Proteins	259	6514	11435	1344
Genes	226	1872	3183	857
Protein Protein Interactions	205	5565	21213	924

Table 2 - CCO protein figures

The core cell cycle proteins are defined as the initial set of proteins collected from the GOA files with an annotation to any term under the “cell cycle” term (GO:0007049) from the GO biological processes subontology. This table shows the number of cell cycle related proteins that were integrated into the system for four model organisms: *A. thaliana* (At), *H. sapiens* (Hs), *S. cerevisiae* (Sc), and *S. pombe* (Sp). Figures are also shown for the composite ontology (CCO): union of the four organism-specific ontologies plus their orthology relationships. The OrthoMCL execution adds more than 13000 new proteins to CCO: 6599 clustered proteins and their 7172 modified versions from UniProt (*e.g.* phosphorylated); the total number of proteins in CCO is **33610**.

Type of proteins	Ontology				
	At	Hs	Sc	Sp	CCO
Core cell cycle	162	870	602	749	2383
Added from IntAct	70	1067	2542	109	3788
Modified proteins added from UniProt	27	4577	8291	486	17985
TOTAL	259	6514	11435	1344	24156

Table 3 - Integrated ontology figures

The integrated CCO contains data from four model organisms (*A. thaliana* [At], *H. sapiens* [Hs], *S. cerevisiae* [Sc], and *S. pombe* [Sp]). Numbers are given for some of the main entities (*e.g.* cell cycle proteins) in the composite ontology (CCO).

Entity	Ontology				
	At	Hs	Sc	Sp	CCO
Proteins	2958	15742	1996	12914	33610
Genes	2100	3919	3474	1246	10739
Orthology types	—	—	—	—	1653